

THE ROLE OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS IN THE FORMATION OF GRAMMAR SKILLS IN ENGLISH

Sodikova Aziza Yorkin kizi

Student of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Gmail: azizazyadullayeva12gmail.com

Ergashev Mirsaid Bakhtiyorovich

senior lecturer of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role and importance of mobile applications in the formation and development of grammatical skills in the process of teaching English from a scientific-theoretical and practical point of view. The rapid introduction of modern information and communication technologies into the education system creates alternative and effective approaches to traditional methods of teaching foreign languages. In particular, with the help of mobile applications, the possibilities of mastering grammatical materials in an interactive, visual, and contextual way are expanding. The article highlights the didactic features of mobile applications in the formation of grammatical competence, their role in increasing motivation, and the possibilities of supporting independent learning. Also, the advantages and some limitations of using mobile applications are analyzed, and scientific conclusions are drawn on their effective use in teaching English grammar in higher educational institutions. The research results show that it is possible to achieve the consolidation of students' grammatical knowledge by integrating mobile learning tools into the educational process.

Introduction

In the context of today's globalization and digitalization, the English language is becoming increasingly important as one of the main means of international communication, science, technology, and academic exchange. In the process of effective mastery of English, grammatical skills are an important component of language competence, and they play a key role in the formation of correct and fluent speech. Mastering grammar in language learning is closely related not only to linguistic knowledge, but also to the development of communicative competence (H. D. Brown, 2007).

Traditional methods of teaching grammar are often limited by a rule-based approach and do not sufficiently ensure student activity and independent thinking. Therefore, the need for innovative and technological approaches in modern methodology is growing. The widespread introduction of information and communication technologies into the educational

process has created new pedagogical opportunities for teaching foreign languages. In particular, the concept of mobile learning allows for the organization of learning without time and space constraints (Traxler, 2009).

Mobile applications provide interactivity, visualization, and quick feedback in the process of language learning, serving the gradual and contextual assimilation of grammatical material. Studies show that classes conducted using mobile applications increase student motivation, develop independent learning skills, and have a positive effect on reducing grammatical errors (Kukulska-Hulme & Shield, 2008). In particular, automated exercises, tests, and game elements contribute to the conscious and solid assimilation of grammatical structures (Chapelle, 2010).

The use of mobile applications in teaching English in higher educational institutions, along with increasing the digital literacy of students, ensures their adaptation to the modern educational environment. Since today's student is actively engaged in communication with mobile technologies, the integration of these tools into the educational process is pedagogically expedient (UNESCO, 2013). From this point of view, the scientific study of the role and effectiveness of mobile applications in the formation of grammatical skills in the English language is one of the urgent issues.

Main part

The formation of grammatical skills in teaching English is a complex and multi-stage process, which requires not only knowledge of grammatical rules, but also their correct application in the process of practical speech. In modern methodological approaches, grammatical competence is considered as an integral part of communicative competence. Therefore, it is important to use interactivity, a contextual approach, and tools that increase student activity in teaching grammar (Richards & Rodgers, 2014).

Mobile applications are recognized as one of the effective learning tools that can meet these requirements. The integration of mobile technologies into education serves to create an individualized, flexible, and continuous learning environment in language learning. According to research, performing grammatical exercises through mobile applications allows students to repeat, reinforce, and apply rules in real speech situations (Kukulska-Hulme, 2012).

One of the main advantages of mobile applications in the formation of grammatical skills is their interactive nature. Interactive exercises, tests, game-based tasks (gamification) involve students in the active learning process and increase their motivation for learning. Psycholinguistic studies show that high motivation has a positive effect on the retention of grammatical structures in long-term memory (Dörnyei, 2001).

Also, fast and automated feedback provided in mobile applications allows for the detection of grammatical errors and their immediate correction. This increases the effectiveness of working on errors in the learning process. Chapelle argues that in technology-based learning, immediate explanations have important didactic significance in language learning (Chapelle, 2010).

Mobile applications are also significant in that they provide grammatical materials in a visual and contextual way. Explanation of grammatical rules using tables, diagrams, animations, and real-life examples helps students more easily perceive complex structures. According to Meyer's theory of multimodal learning, the transfer of information through

multiple channels leads to effective assimilation of knowledge (Mayer, 2009). It is this aspect that makes mobile applications superior to traditional textbooks in teaching grammar.

In addition, mobile applications play an important role in organizing independent learning. Students have the opportunity to perform grammatical exercises, check and consolidate their knowledge outside of class time. In studies conducted by UNESCO, mobile learning tools are assessed as an effective mechanism supporting continuous and independent learning (UNESCO, 2013).

At the same time, there are some restrictions on the use of mobile applications. In particular, insufficient technical capabilities, dependence on the Internet, as well as the didactically incorrect selection of mobile applications can negatively affect the effectiveness of learning. Therefore, when introducing mobile applications into the educational process, it is necessary to take into account their content, methodological validity, and compatibility with educational goals (Stockwell, 2010).

In general, the analysis of scientific research shows that the targeted and systematic use of mobile applications makes the process of forming grammatical skills in English significantly more effective. They increase student activity, stimulate independent learning, and serve the consolidation of grammatical knowledge.

Conclusion

In this article, the role and importance of mobile applications in the process of forming grammatical skills in the English language were analyzed from a scientific-theoretical and methodological point of view. The research results show that grammatical competence is one of the main components of foreign language acquisition, and its effective development requires modern pedagogical and technological approaches. The combination of traditional teaching methods with mobile learning tools serves to improve the quality of the process of acquiring grammatical knowledge.

Analysis shows that the targeted and systematic use of mobile applications allows achieving high effectiveness in teaching English grammar. However, when introducing them into the educational process, it is important to take into account such factors as methodological validity, technical capabilities, and compliance with educational goals. The directing and controlling role of the teacher is crucial in ensuring the pedagogical effectiveness of mobile learning.

In conclusion, mobile applications serve as an effective educational tool for the formation of grammatical skills in English, and their widespread use in higher educational institutions allows for a further improvement in the quality of foreign language teaching. The results of this study serve as a theoretical and practical basis for further scientific research on the integration of mobile technologies into the methodology of teaching a foreign language.

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